

RECRUITMENT, SELECTION AND INTEGRATION IN THE HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Gabriel Ionuț VASILE, PhD
University of Valahia Targoviste

Xiaoyu ZHAN, PhD
University of Valahia Targoviste
instructiuni.ssm@yahoo.com

Abstract: *In the human resource field, in order to be successful and especially to survive, organisations in general and companies, in particular, have to settle the following aspects: to identify the qualifications and skills and to choose the candidates that suit best the requirements of the vacancy or newly created jobs; to identify and attract competitive candidates using the most appropriate methods, sources or head hunting environments; to comply with the legislation in the field regarding equal opportunities for employment and to correct the existing discriminatory practices or some imbalances.*

Keywords: *Recruitment, Internal Recruitment, External Recruitment, Selection, Job*

JEL classification: *M12, 012*

Recruitment and selection of personnel

Recruitment

The process of searching, localization, attraction of potential candidates, from whom capable candidates are to be selected, who eventually show the necessary professional characteristics or who best correspond to the requirements of current and future vacancy jobs (Câmpeanu-Sonea & Osoian, 2004, p. 101).

The recruitment process generally includes all the stages that the organisation proposes to pursue in order to search the corresponding candidate to fill a vacancy job.

- Prepare the recruitment
- Analyse the application

- Job description
- Define the candidate profile
- Search candidacies
- External candidacies. Recruitment sources
- Recruitment announcement campaign
- Select the candidates

Characteristics:

- it is an interaction process between organisation and candidates where parties can attract or reject each other;
- it is a bi-dimensional process where the candidate should be satisfied with the organisation, and the organisation with the candidate involved in the process;
- it is a double-way communication process where the parties send each other signals;
- requires compromises between the parties for the harmonisation of their requirements and preferences
- requires full transparency of both parties, it has to be based on accurate and real data and information that can be tested in any moment.

In the management practice, there are several methods that can be used to recruit potential employees:

- advertising
- acquaintance network
- use of counsellors
- search of persons
- file with potential candidates

Advertising

Advertising is a vital element for the recruitment process. The objective pursued should be to penetrate the labour market as deep as possible with a very attractive employment offer, conceived so that it determines a corresponding reaction from two perspectives:

- a) of requests for further information and
- b) of number of applications submitted.

The efficiency of an employment ad can be appreciated according to:

- the number of requests for further information;
- the number of the requests for employment;
- the degree compatibility of the employees with the conditions expressed.

Mentioning the age, sex, religion, or nationality for a candidate who is not taken into consideration should be avoided. This is considered discrimination, which is sanctioned by law (Lefter, Deaconu, 2009, p. 113).

In order to be efficient, an employment ad should:

- state the main employment and labour conditions, including the level of salary for such job;
 - present the organisation and/or its object of activity with some concise references;
 - specify how and to whom the requests for employment should be sent;
 - provide concise, but adequate details regarding the outstanding characteristics of the job;
 - present all of the above under a concise, yet attractive form;
- comply with the legal regulations;
- summary the essential personal features that the job holder should have;

Generally, the attributes that an employment ad need to have to be efficient should cover the following aspects:

- to present the organisation and/or its object of activity with some concise references;
- to provide concise, but adequate details regarding the outstanding characteristics of the job;
- to summary the essential personal features that the job holder should have;
- to state the main employment and labour conditions, including the level of salary for such job;
- to specify how and to whom the requests for employment should be sent;
- to present all of the above under a concise, yet attractive form;
- to comply with the legal regulations.

Avoid mentioning the age, sex, religion, or nationality for a candidate who is not taken into consideration. This is considered discrimination, which is sanctioned by law. For example, in case of hiring storekeeper or manager, the law imposes to be minimum 21 years old, which is advisable to be mentioned in the employment ad – a first selection of candidates is made.

Internal Recruitment

Advantages:

- the organisations have the possibilities to get to know much better the candidates' "strengths" and "weaknesses", because there are enough information on them;

- it is much easier to attract candidates because they are much more known or remarked due to their performed activity;
- the selection according to organisation criteria is much faster and more efficient, because the candidates coming from the inside of the organisation have much more knowledge on organisation practices, which leads to less time to accommodate and integrate on the job;
- although many jobs belonging to some different organisations are similar, only the internal recruitment allows us to obtain the particular qualifications or knowledge and the experience required by some jobs;
- the probability to make inadequate decisions is much diminished due to the higher amount of information on the employees;
- personnel recruitment is, in many situations, much faster and less costly, even if an additional training of candidates is necessary;
- the time corresponding to job counselling of the new employees, for their integration as rapidly as possible, is much more diminished;
- the feeling of belonging to organisation, of loyalty or attachment to it, increases;
- the probability that employees have inadequate expectations or perspectives or that they become disappointed and dissatisfied with the organisation, is much more reduced;
- the motivation of the personnel increases, and the moral environment improves, because the promotion opportunities are incentive, at the same time being considered as important compensations for many employees.

Disadvantages:

- lack of promotions or contribution of some "new ideas", of some "new or fresh openings";
- the recruitment policy within the organization can suppose erroneously that the employees considered (for promotion) have the necessary qualities or the adequate potential to be promoted, under the circumstances in which their former activity is also interrupted with no reason;
- it favours the manifestation of Peter' principle, according to which people tend to climb the hierarchy ladder until their level of incompetence or, in other words, the employees are promoted until they reach a level where they are not capable any more to act adequately; it means that employees can be promoted, if accomplishing the tasks

adequately, until they reach such jobs whose demands are higher than their potential;

- favouritism can appear, or many conflict or affective moods (agitation, hostility, resistance, open aggression etc.) can activate, determined by the different way of perception of some facts or situations
- the hope of employees in promotion is not substantiated, they become indifferent, which eventually leads to their demoralization, to decrease of performance and sometimes to resignations.

External Recruitment

Advantages:

- it offers more options to choose the desired candidate;
- the possibility of attracting some persons with an outstanding professional training;
- although the costs of new employments are significant, there are cases when they are more reduced than the ones necessary to train the internal personnel in order to get some new positions.

Disadvantages:

- the identification, attraction and assessment of candidates is much more difficult if we take into consideration the complexity of the labour market and the fact that the skills or other requirements of the new employees are not assessed directly, but based on some references or on some short-time meetings during interviews;
- the risk of hiring candidates who subsequently prove not to have or cannot keep the high potential they have shown during the selection process;
- the cost of personnel recruitment is much higher due to identification and attraction of candidates from a wide, less known and more difficult "to accede" labour market, the resources of time and money are much higher;
- the time necessary to counselling, adaptation or integration on positions of the new employees is much higher, attracting additional costs;
- when there are frequent employments outside the organisation, the potential internal candidates can feel frustrated, there can be some resentfulness, discouragement, even some major problems or some moral issues among its own employees, who consider that they meet the necessary conditions, but their chances of promotion are reduced.

Selection

The selection activities aim at identifying the most suitable candidates and to convince them to enter the organisation.

A well-managed selection process, carried out pursuant to the methodology presented, creates an added value in the organisation, because there are sensible differences between a correctly selected employee, loyal to the organisation, with significant performances, and another one, who makes a minimum effort, has modest results, working only to get paid.

A modest employee will impose his/her standard to his/her co-workers, and that is why it is necessary that the selection should avoid as much as possible a part of the costs, which are difficult to estimate, of an unfortunate employment.

The main stages of the selection process are:

- to select the applications or the CVs;
- to make a final (limited) list with candidates;
- to invite these candidates to an interview;
- to carry out the interviews (and the auxiliary tests, if appropriate);
- to make a decision regarding the selected candidates;
- to draft and confirm an attractive offer;
- to notify the rejected candidates in writing;
- to inform the managers regarding the decisions made.

The Interview should offer information on three categories of problems:

- Can the candidate perform the activity provided by the job?
- Does the candidate wish to perform the activity provided by the job?
- Can the candidate integrate into the team where he/she is going to work?

There are a few clear rules for interviews:

- The candidate should be determined to talk as much as possible;
- The environment of the interview should be quiet in order to create a calm and relaxed atmosphere;
- There should not be any interruptions from the outside;
- The interviewer team (it is better to be a team, not one person) should be well-prepared for the interview, to know the job and the candidate file.

Key points in personnel recruitment and selection:

- Recruitment and selection are costly processes.
- The entire fairness of the process can be assured by a thorough analysis of the job and by comparing the particularities and the skills of those who are to occupy it.
- The initial impression on people is usually inaccurate, and if we acted according to it, we would reach inaccurate and poor quality selection decisions.
- The job analysis is a crucial element for the success of the recruitment and selection process.
- The mistakes made at this stage reflect on the entire process.
- The purpose of recruitment is to attract a small number of correspondingly qualified applicants.
- The limited list of candidates to be invited to an interview is made up following the comparison between the capacity and the experience of each applicant, and the job description.

Recruitment, selection and integration in human resources management requires a complex, extensive activity of searching and finding potential candidates for organizations that have vacancies so that they fit the standards, objectives and purpose of the organization.

References

- Câmpeanu-Sonea, E., & Osoian, C. (2004). *Managementul resursei umane, Recrutarea, selecția și dezvoltarea profesională (Human resource management, Recruitment, selection and professional development)*. Cluj-Napoca: Press Universitars Clujeana.
- Lefter V., & Deaconu A. (2009). *Managementul Resurselor Umane. Teorie si practica. (Human resource management. Theory and practice)* Bucharest: Economica Publishing House.